

PROBLEMS OF TECHNICAL TERMS TRANSLATION

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Abstract: The given article describes the problems of transport terms that students come across and some ways of their interpretation. Topics were discussed concerning the necessity of systematization of terms and enhancing the implementation of linguistic methods of their formation. As there written in the article, learning railway terms and making accurate translation is a time-consuming and labor intensive process which requires not only good knowledge of target language, but native one as well.

Key words: issue, terms, translation, process.

Scientific and technical translation occupies a special place among other types of translation. This position follows from the informative characteristics of technical texts and the specific features of their linguistic means. Such language means are terms and precision words, i.e. Units of translation with fixed semasiological links or links of a linguistic sign with a denoter. Semasiological connections can be constant or temporary, fixed or non-fixed, expressed or erased.

Terms, not being a special group of words, but representing a special quality of ordinary words, hamper the translation process, if their presentation does not cause association at the level of semantic information, i.e. Information contained in the utterance and transmitted through the value of units of language.

A feature of any terminological vocabulary is its hierarchical construction in the form of a series of closed micro systems. Awareness of the hierarchy of terms promotes their better understanding, and, consequently, the realization of the operation of scientific and technical translation. Scientific and technical translation is characterized by a high coefficient of information content of source texts and the presence of terms as the dominant language units in the texts of translation, since the term carries in itself not secondary, but key information. Such information also predetermines the effect of the translator. The correct translation of the term is possible only if you know the equivalents of the two languages and the ability to distinguish the denotation they denote from the surrounding reality.

The term is an emotionally neutral word or phrase that is used to express the concept or the name of objects accurately. Translation of terms requires

knowledge of the industry to which the translation relates, understanding of the content of the text. Knowledge of the subject. The interaction of the term with the context is important. This helps to clarify the meaning of the word. Translator's task: to determine the meaning of the term in the context of the source language and to convey the denotative meaning of the word in the target language.

The main method of translation is the search for a lexical equivalent, i.e. Of-the-lexical correspondence. The interpreter must be able to find the equivalent in the target language and thus create an adequate perception. The difficulties of translation are explained by the fact that there are general scientific, general technical and narrowly specialized terms. The former are used in several branches. The latter are used only in one of the branches. The terms can be multi-valued, synonymous or homonymous.

All terms in the form are divided into:

- 1.Simple - circuit (circuit), flexibility (flexibility)
- 2.Complicated - flywheel (flywheel), nonlinear (nonlinear), non-waste (waste-free)
3. The word combinations are a circuit breaker, non-metallic inclusions, a multi-scale process, heat and mass exchange, wide spectrum properties, The most difficult to translate are terminology, in which each word is independent. The components of such terms can be separated into an independent unit. For example, brake gear - a brake mechanism, electric motor - electric motor, powder materials - powder materials.

The most difficult to translate are terms

- a) the meaning of which results from the combination of 2 words load governor - load regulator, brake landing - landing with braking;
- b) the components of which are decorated with the help of grammatical components: ways of measurement - the methods of measurement, body of reactor - the editor's body, breaking with rocket - torpedo using a rocket engine; Lid of frame - housing cover.

Among other types of terms, the difficulty in translating is represented by phrases consisting of such structures:

- a) noun + noun: back-coupling - feedback; Variable - capacitor - variable capacitor; Peak - energy - maximum energy; Phase transition - phase transitions, percussion waves - shock waves
- b) adjective + essential: remote control - remote control; Safety switch - emergency switch; Direct current;

c) participle + essential: alternating current - alternating current;
Calculating theory - theory of calculation

d) gerundive + noun: estimated cost - project cost, unbounded stream - free flow.

If the second component or both components of the word combination are common terms, then the translation does not present a special complexity. For example, safety switch is an emergency switch, line wire is live, thermal stress is thermal stress.

It should be borne in mind that one and the same form of words can have different meanings in different branches of the same sphere of science and technology. For example, "airframe" in aircraft construction has the meaning of a "glider", and in the space industry this is the "missile body". The word "fuel" in conventional energy matters "fuel," and in nuclear power it is "nuclear fuel." Thus, when translating terms in a technical text, the translator should focus on the subject matter of the text in order to avoid the wrongly chosen version of the translation of the homonymous term.

When translating a scientific and technical text, the translator should first of all exclude background information, identify the key information and find a foreign language equivalent, in other words, identify the denoter in the target language.

From all that has been said, it follows that the translator must:

- 1) To know at least one foreign language in a degree sufficient for understanding.
- 2) To know another language (usually native) in a degree sufficient for a competent presentation.

3) Be able to use working sources of information.

4) Be able to do different types of translation.

There are several important conclusions to be drawn. Inability to ignore the concrete forms of words and inability to use the context to clarify their meaning is one of the typical mistakes in translation. It is necessary to be distracted from specific forms of words and learn use the context to clarify their meaning.

No word of the original should be transferred into translation, except for the words (and expressions) of another foreign language, Encased in the original.

Old words sometimes receive qualitatively new meanings.

Individual words outside the context do not have a specific meaning and therefore can't be translated. Not words are translated, but what they express.

The investigation is the first. If the translation is a transfer of what is already

it was expressed, then, means, not words, grammatical constructions and other means of the original language are transferred, but thoughts, the content of the original.

The second consequence. If translation is an expression of what has already been expressed in any language, then there are no untranslatable texts. That, What can be expressed in one language, can be expressed on any other. There are only difficultly translated texts. Moreover, difficulties in translating are difficulties connected with understanding, which result from insufficient knowledge of the original language or insufficient knowledge of the subject matter, that is, from a lack of special knowledge. Or difficulties associated with expression, which are due to the poor knowledge of the language on which the translation is made, or the lack of ready-made equivalents in this language for expressing what has already been expressed in the means of the original language. Thus, it is not a matter of what is being translated, but in the way it is translated and for what. Technical translation is, first of all, a translation used for special purposes, namely for the exchange of special information coming in and perceived in different languages.

Thus, the closest semantically translated from English technical text in Russian is largely determined by general technical training of translators, knowing their art knowledge in the first place, but also remember that the translatable their technical terminology in a specialized text is replete with a variety of sometimes complicated challenges, as referred to above.

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